

Biological Definition of Neuronal alpha-Synuclein Disease: Towards an Integrated Staging System for Research

Authors: Tanya Simuni, MD*¹, Lana M. Chahine, MD*², Kathleen Poston, MD, MS³, Michael Brumm, MS⁴, Teresa Buracchio, MD⁵, Michelle Campbell, PhD⁵, Sohini Chowdhury, MA⁶, Christopher Coffey, PhD⁴, Luis Concha-Marambio, PhD⁷, Tien Dam, MD⁸, Peter DiBiaso, MHSA^{9,10}, Tatiana Foroud, PhD¹¹, Mark Frasier, PhD⁶, Caroline Gochanour, MS⁴, Danna Jennings, MD, BSN¹², Karl Kieburtz, MD, MPH¹³, Catherine M. Kopil, PhD⁶, Kalpana Merchant, PhD¹, Brit Mollenhauer, MD¹⁴, Thomas Montine, MD, PhD¹⁵, Kelly Nudelman, PhD¹¹, Gennaro Pagano, MD, MS, PhD, eMBA¹⁶, John Seibyl, MD¹⁷, Todd Sherer, PhD⁶, Andrew Singleton, PhD¹⁸, Diane Stephenson, PhD¹⁹, Matthew Stern, MD²⁰, Claudio Soto, PhD^{7,21}, Caroline M. Tanner, MD, PhD²², Eduardo Tolosa, MD²³, Daniel Weintraub, MD²⁴, Yuge Xiao, B.S.⁶, Andrew Siderowf, MD²⁰, Billy Dunn, MD²⁵, Kenneth Marek, MD¹⁷.

*Contributed equally

1. Department of Neurology, Northwestern University Feinberg School of Medicine, Chicago, IL, USA.
2. Department of Neurology, University of Pittsburgh, Pittsburgh, PA, USA.
3. Department of Neurology, Stanford University School of Medicine, Palo Alto, CA, USA.
4. Department of Biostatistics, College of Public Health, University of Iowa, Iowa City, IA, USA.
5. Center for Drug Evaluation and Research, Food and Drug Administration, Silver Spring, MD, USA.
6. The Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research, New York, NY, USA.
7. Amprion Inc., San Diego, CA, USA.
8. Biogen, Cambridge, MA, USA.
9. Patient Council, The Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research, New York, NY, USA
10. Clinical Solutions and Strategic Partnerships, WCG Clinical, Princeton, NJ, USA.
11. Department of Medical and Molecular Genetics, Indiana University, Indianapolis, IN, USA.
12. Denali Therapeutics Inc., South San Francisco, CA, USA.
13. Department of Neurology, University of Rochester Medical Center, Rochester, NY, USA.
14. Department of Neurology, University Medical Center Göttingen and Paracelsus-Elena-Klinik, Kassel, Germany.
15. Department of Pathology, Stanford University School of Medicine, Stanford, CA, USA.
16. F. Hoffmann-La Roche Ltd., Basel, Switzerland.
17. Institute for Neurodegenerative Disorders, New Haven, CT, USA.
18. National Institute on Aging, National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, MD, USA.
19. Critical Path for Parkinson's, Critical Path Institute, Tucson, AZ, USA.
20. Department of Neurology, Perelman School of Medicine, University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia, PA, USA.
21. Mitchell Center for Alzheimer's Disease and Related Brain Disorders, Department of Neurology, University of Texas McGovern Medical School at Houston, Houston, TX, USA
22. Movement Disorders and Neuromodulation Center, Department of Neurology, Weill Institute for Neuroscience, University of California, San Francisco, CA, USA; Parkinson's Disease Research Education and Clinical Center, San Francisco Veteran's Affairs Health Care System, San Francisco, CA, USA.
23. Parkinson's Disease and Movement Disorders Unit, Neurology Service, Hospital Clínic de Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain; Centro de Investigación Biomédica en Red Sobre Enfermedades Neurodegenerativas (CIBERNED), Hospital Clínic, IDIBAPS, Universitat de Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain.
24. University of Pennsylvania and the Parkinson's Disease and Mental Illness Research, Education and Clinical Centers (PADRECC and MIRECC), Philadelphia Veterans Affairs Medical Center
25. Senior Advisor, The Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research, New York, NY, USA.

Corresponding Author

Tanya Simuni, MD
Department of Neurology
Northwestern University Feinberg School of Medicine
710 North Lake Shore Drive, 1126
Chicago, IL 60611
Phone 312-503-2970
Fax 312-908-5073
tsimuni@nm.org

Abstract word count: 298
Manuscript word count: 5,912
Title Character Count: 108

Tables: 3
Figures: 2
Supplementary Tables / Figures: 1

Running title: Neuronal Alpha-Synuclein Disease

Key words: Biological definition, Neuronal Alpha-Synuclein Disease, Parkinson's disease, Dementia with Lewy Bodies

Abstract

Parkinson's disease (PD) and dementia with Lewy bodies (DLB) are currently defined by their clinical features with alpha-synuclein (asyn) pathology as the gold standard to establish the definitive diagnosis. We propose that given biomarker advances enabling accurate detection of pathologic asyn *in vivo* using the Seed Amplification Assay, it is time to finally redefine PD and DLB based on biology as "Neuronal alpha-Synuclein Disease (NSD)" rather than as clinical syndromes. A biologic definition for PD and DLB is a major shift, but simply reflects that we now have the tools to assess the gold standard required for diagnosis, pathological neuronal-asyn (n-asyn), during life. NSD is defined by presence of pathologic n-asyn species detected *in vivo* (S) independent of any specific clinical syndrome. We further propose that individuals with n-asyn are at risk for dopaminergic neuronal dysfunction (D), the second biologic anchor for NSD. The biological definition allows us to propose a staging system, the NSD Integrated Staging System (NSD-ISS), rooted in the biological anchors (S and D) and degree of functional impairment caused by clinical signs/symptoms. Stages 0-1 are without signs/symptoms and defined by presence of pathogenic variants in *SNCA* gene (Stage 0), S alone (Stage 1A) or S and D (Stage 1B). Presence of clinical manifestations marks transition to Stage 2 and beyond. Stage 2 is characterized by subtle signs/symptoms but no functional impairment. Stages 2B-6 require both S and D and stage-specific increases in functional impairment. NSD definition and NSD-ISS research framework are essential to advancing biologically-targeted therapeutics and enabling interventional trials at early disease stages. The NSD-ISS will evolve, including incorporation of data-driven definition of stage-specific functional anchors and additional biomarkers, as they emerge and are validated. Presently, NSD-ISS is intended for research use only; its application in the clinical setting is premature and inappropriate.

Introduction

Parkinson's disease (PD) and dementia with Lewy bodies (DLB) are currently defined by their clinical features with alpha-synuclein (asyn) pathology as the gold standard that establishes the definitive diagnosis. Numerous clinical diagnostic criteria have been proposed over decades and widely used to classify individuals with PD and DLB. Clinical staging, such as the Hoehn and Yahr Scale, has been developed and utilized to describe disease severity. The problem with these clinical definitions and staging is two-fold. First, the clinical syndromes and clinical progression are heterogeneous with overlap among disorders. Second, converging biomarker, clinical, epidemiologic and neuropathological data clearly demonstrate that pathology begins long before any symptoms or signs, but clinical criteria cannot define PD or DLB during this prolonged period of neurodegeneration.

These problems could be solved by biomarkers that measure *in vivo* misfolded, pathological predominantly neuronal alpha-synuclein (n-asyn), the pathologic hallmark of PD and DLB. Until recently, n-asyn could only be reliably measured post-mortem. In 2016, an assay¹, now known as seed amplification assay (SAA), was developed that could detect n-asyn *in vivo* with high accuracy. Its rapid, rigorous optimization and validation²⁻⁶ has been a landmark advancement for the field. We propose that given our ability to detect n-asyn using SAA, it is time to finally redefine PD and DLB based on biology rather than as clinical syndromes. We recognize that a biologic definition for PD and DLB is a major shift, but it simply reflects that we now have the tools to establish the gold standard diagnosis during life.

We suggest that a biologic definition allows us to combine PD and DLB under the term Neuronal alpha-Synuclein Disease (NSD), defined by *in vivo* detection of n-asyn (S). We further propose that individuals with n-asyn are at high risk for developing dopaminergic neuronal dysfunction (D), a second key biologic anchor for NSD. Defining NSD by its biology is crucial to further understanding disease pathophysiology, enabling biology-specific therapeutic development⁷ and therapeutic intervention prior to symptom onset to potentially prevent/halt progression⁸, and identifying biologically-defined subsets⁹.

Two centuries after PD was first described¹⁰ and three decades since the term DLB was proposed¹¹, the field now has the knowledge and tools to redefine these entities based on biology and conceptualize a staging system rooted in biology. We propose an integrated biologic and clinical staging system for NSD that begins at the start of disease, when it is still asymptomatic, and continues through the development of increasing severity of functional impairment. The key rationale for a staging system is to accelerate therapeutic development in all disease stages, critically including those defined by biomarkers prior to the onset of symptoms as well as those in later stages, anchored by clinical features. Our approach of defining the disease based on biology and biomarkers builds on similar efforts in other neurodegenerative diseases, including Alzheimer's disease (AD)^{12,13} and Huntington's disease (HD)¹⁴.

We present the definition of NSD and our concept for the NSD integrated staging system (NSD-ISS), providing examples of how this proposed biologic definition and staging system will advance the field. We propose that a conceptual framework for NSD staging is crucial to accelerate NSD drug development, just as AD staging has accelerated AD drug development. This inaugural version of the NSD-ISS is intended for research use only; its application in the clinical setting is premature and inappropriate. We urge the research community to work together to provide the data to test this concept fully. We highlight key outstanding questions and opportunities for the NSD-ISS to facilitate further investigation, which in turn will inform future iterations of the staging system.

Process

Details on the process for development of the NSD definition and NSD-ISS are provided in the appendix page 1. Briefly, in 2022, in the setting of broad consensus among a range of stakeholders that biological

definition and staging of alpha-synucleinopathies was critical to advancing therapeutic development¹⁵, a working group was assembled under auspices of The Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research (MJFF). This working group includes international neuroscience and clinical experts, industry sponsors, disease focused non-profit organizations, regulatory authorities, and representatives of the patient community. Focusing on an approach grounded in existing data, the objectives were to: (1) develop a biologic definition for disease; (2) develop a framework for a disease staging that delineates disease stages to accelerate targeted therapeutics (3) identify key gaps in knowledge. Following a series of virtual meetings, a face-to-face conference was held in January 2023. Following this conference and a series of weekly virtual meetings, seven international non-profit organizations, including MJFF, supported a face-to-face roundtable and subsequent virtual summit. These events were held in April 2023 with diverse stakeholders, including an expanded group of global NSD neuroscience and clinical experts, patient community, public-private partnership groups, representatives from industry and regulatory agencies, and additional patient advocacy groups. Several key revisions to the NSD-ISS resulted. The draft manuscript was posted for public comment and key feedback was incorporated.

Search Strategy and Selection Criteria

Relevant articles were identified from three main sources: keyword-based searches of PubMed, with selection of articles based on relevance, key citations included within relevant articles, and nomination of articles by authors or during public comment. The initial PubMed search was conducted in January 2022 and updated through August 2023. PubMed was searched using free text search terms for English language articles pertaining to: diagnostic criteria for Lewy body disorders, the role of asyn in pathophysiology, other relevant molecular pathways, including genetics, *in vivo* biomarkers of asyn, dopaminergic dysfunction and imaging biomarkers for it, and clinical manifestations of alpha-synucleinopathies across the continuum.

Unifying Terminology

Neuronal alpha-synucleinopathies, defined by accumulation of disease-specific¹⁶⁻¹⁸ pathological asyn predominantly in neuronal cell bodies and neurites (Lewy bodies and Lewy neurites), may be asymptomatic or may manifest clinically with parkinsonism, cognitive impairment, and an array of other motor and non-motor manifestations. Based on the sequence and progression of clinical signs/symptoms, individuals have been designated with varying terms¹⁹⁻²⁶, such as incidental Lewy body disease²⁷, preclinical (without clinical features), premotor, Pure Autonomic Failure (PAF), idiopathic REM-Sleep Behavior Disorder (iRBD), other prodromal (early signs/symptoms, not yet fulfilling clinical diagnostic criteria for a disease), or as having a possible or probable clinical diagnosis of PD, PD dementia (PDD), or DLB.

NSD is proposed as a *new unifying term defined by biology to encompass all alpha-synucleinopathies with n-asyn—that is, predominantly neuronal deposition of misfolded pathologic asyn.*

NSD Definition

NSD is defined by presence of n-asyn (S) and stage-dependent evidence of dopaminergic neuronal dysfunction (D). In addition, presence of fully penetrant pathogenic variants in the SNCA gene (G) is sufficient for NSD diagnosis. The current measures used to determine an individual's S or D status are categorical (positive/negative) but are anticipated to become quantitative as the field evolves.

Central tenets of the biologic definition of NSD are: (1) the *disease* is defined biologically based on objective *in vivo* biomarkers (2) the disease can be diagnosed in absence of clinical manifestations and (3) clinical manifestations in the absence of biomarkers are not sufficient to diagnose the disease.

S/D/G anchors of the NSD-ISS: description of *in vivo* biomarkers

S anchor: n-asyn

Presence of n-asyn (S+) is the defining feature of NSD and key to the NSD-ISS staging framework.

Over a century ago, Lewy bodies were identified as the pathologic hallmark of disorders now encompassed in the definition of NSD²⁸. Landmark discoveries included identification of the p.A53T *SNCA* variant as a cause for PD and determination that asyn was the core constituent of Lewy bodies and Lewy neurites²⁹. The key role of n-asyn pathology in NSD is well established based on extensive pathologic, molecular and genetic evidence in animal models and in humans, as recently reviewed³⁰.

Any rigorously validated and accurate biomarker of n-asyn can be used to assess for NSD. Efforts to identify and measure pathological asyn *in vivo* have been underway for over two decades. Several measures of n-asyn have been investigated and show promising results, as recently reviewed elsewhere in detail^{31,32}. However, at present, only CSF asyn SAA has undergone robust validation. This includes demonstration of consistent results in two different studies conducted at multiple independent laboratories using well-characterized blinded samples^{33,34}, and high accuracy when tested in a double blind fashion in multiple, independent, multicenter cohorts^{2-4,6}. CSF asyn SAA thus meets the level of evidence required to reliably diagnose NSD. This assay is positive in >95% of autopsy-confirmed cases of PD and DLB^{5,35} and identifies individuals with clinical signs/symptoms of PD and DLB with high accuracy^{2-4,6}. SAA also detects n-asyn in individuals with iRBD, olfactory or autonomic dysfunction, and genetic risk who are more likely to progress to clinically defined PD or DLB^{2,36-38}. Importantly, a positive CSF asyn SAA in cognitively intact individuals³⁹ and in individuals with isolated hyposmia⁴⁰ was associated with progression to clinically defined alpha-synucleinopathies within 4-6 years. Critically, this assay can distinguish n-asyn from other asyn forms, specifically those associated with the predominantly glial pathology of Multiple System Atrophy (MSA)^{41,42}.

Standard operating procedures and best practices for biospecimen handling⁴³ are critical for accurate application of asyn SAA. Currently, the most widely-applied assay^{2,44} uses maximal fluorescence emitted during aggregation to define positivity for n-asyn and distinguish NSD from healthy individuals and those with MSA.

As mentioned, several other measures of n-asyn are being studied, and it is expected that other reliable n-asyn biomarkers will emerge. These include SAA in other matrices such as blood and peripheral tissue^{3,31,45-47}. Other measures of n-asyn besides SAA also hold promise. Immunohistochemical detection of phosphorylated n-asyn in skin biopsies demonstrates high accuracy for distinguishing NSD from controls^{48,49} and clinically-diagnosed PD from MSA^{46,50}. In addition, disease-specific post-translational modifications of asyn and exosome-derived asyn biomarkers are also being studied³¹. The NSD-ISS research framework enables incorporation of any emerging measures alongside or instead of SAA to determine presence of n-asyn (S), once they have been rigorously replicated, reproduced, and validated.

A major goal is to develop quantitative measures of n-asyn. Intensive efforts are also underway to develop PET tracers for topographical *in vivo* detection of n-asyn^{51,52}.

NSD is associated with a widespread distribution of n-asyn aggregation both in the peripheral and central nervous system³¹. Whether pathological changes occur first in the periphery or concurrent to the central nervous system is unknown. The NSD-ISS framework can incorporate both peripheral and additional central biomarkers of n-asyn pathology once such are validated.

D anchor: dopaminergic neuron dysfunction/degeneration

Degeneration of substantia nigra dopaminergic neurons (D) is a core pathological feature and a second key anchor of NSD. Evidence of dopaminergic neuron dysfunction/degeneration itself is not specific to NSD, but when combined with a biomarker of n-*asyn* is central to the definition of NSD.

Loss of midbrain dopaminergic neurons was identified as a key pathology in PD about 75 years ago and soon after, symptomatic benefit from dopamine replacement was demonstrated⁵³. There are extensive data showing that dopaminergic dysfunction is present in an overwhelming majority of S+ individuals not only with predominantly motor but also cognitive, or other non-motor, signs/symptoms of NSD^{2,54-58}.

Molecular imaging of the dopamine system has been widely used to detect dopamine dysfunction in life. Dopaminergic imaging with fluorodopa, tracers for the dopamine transporter (DAT), or vesicular monoamine transporter (VMAT) effectively mirror striatal pathologic change in dopaminergic regions, showing the expected asymmetric, rostral-caudal striatal loss^{59,60}. In addition, DAT binding correlates with neuronal density⁶¹ and nigral cell counts⁶² in brains of individuals with neurodegenerative disorders. Importantly, >88% of DLB cases diagnosed based on clinical diagnostic criteria or on pathology have abnormal DAT single photon emission tomography (SPECT)⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶.

Studies have clearly demonstrated that DAT loss occurs before functional impairment, and further that individuals without functional impairment with DAT deficit are likely to progress to develop functional impairment within 3-5 years. For example, reduced DAT binding in people with olfactory dysfunction or iRBD predicts motor and cognitive progression⁶³⁻⁶⁷. Similarly, individuals with motor signs/symptoms without DAT deficit are unlikely to have n-*asyn* and to progress to severe functional impairment^{2,68,69}.

Currently, DAT SPECT imaging using ioflupane (I¹²³) is the most widely utilized tracer to assess DAT binding, both in research and clinical practice. Based on current data, a quantitative DAT SPECT biomarker, the specific binding ratio in the lowest putamen adjusted for age and sex, is used to categorize individuals as DAT deficit (D+) or without DAT deficit (D-). Standardized DAT acquisition and analysis are essential. Several analysis protocols are utilized for DAT measurement. A goal will be to harmonize these outcomes to provide a unified field standard. Data from several studies including Parkinson Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI)⁷⁰ and recent clinical trials⁷¹ are available to establish this quantitative standard.

There are also limited but evolving data showing that several PET tracers targeting DAT or VMAT effectively detect dopaminergic dysfunction^{60,72,73}. These PET tracers might be an alternative to ioflupane imaging. All PET and SPECT dopamine tracer data can ultimately be harmonized to a single quantitative scale similar to centiloids for amyloid imaging⁷⁴, thereby enabling the incorporation of quantitative measures of DAT binding into future iterations of the NSD-ISS. Several other promising imaging modalities exist that detect dysfunction in the dopaminergic system *in vivo*, including neuromelanin-sensitive MRI^{72,73}. The NSD-ISS research framework enables incorporation of any emerging measures of dopaminergic dysfunction in addition to or instead of DAT, once they have been rigorously replicated, reproduced, and validated.

Importantly, current data strongly suggest that n-*asyn* can be detected by SAA before dopamine dysfunction is detectable by imaging^{2,40,75}. While the overwhelming majority of individuals develop detectable DAT loss prior to functional impairment⁶³⁻⁶⁷, signs/symptoms and functional impairment may occur in S+ individuals in the absence of DAT deficit. Additional data will clarify how frequently and under what conditions this may occur. Further, we acknowledge that presynaptic dopaminergic dysfunction is not specific for NSD⁷³.

NSD is a multisystem disease that may involve neuronal degeneration widely in the central, autonomic, and peripheral nervous system involving both dopaminergic and non-dopaminergic pathways⁷⁶. With validation of imaging and other biomarkers that reflect NSD-specific neurodegeneration will come opportunities to incorporate them into the NSD-ISS. Ultimately, we envision that a measure of neurodegeneration (“N”) beyond dopaminergic dysfunction will be an anchor in the staging system.

G status

Genetic variants may either cause or increase risk for NSD. Fully penetrant pathogenic variants in *SNCA*⁷⁷, the gene that encodes asyn, are disease-defining in the NSD-ISS. Individuals with these rare variants have a high certainty of developing n-asyn pathology. Other genetic variants (G) identify individuals who may have increased age-dependent risk (R), but these individuals do not have NSD unless they demonstrate evidence of n-asyn (S+).

Genetics play a pivotal role in understanding NSD biology, genetically-driven disease subtyping, and guiding therapeutic development. Pathogenic variants in numerous genes are associated with NSD⁷⁸⁻⁸⁰. Approximately 10-15% of clinically-diagnosed PD cases carry pathogenic variants, most commonly in *GBAI* and *LRRK2*⁸¹. Pathogenic variants in *GBAI* have also been identified in individuals with a clinical diagnosis of DLB⁷⁹. These variants confer varied risk that is variant-dependent and increases with age⁸². Some less common genetic variants have high penetrance, such as bi-allelic pathogenic variants in *VPS13C*, *VPS35*, *PARK7*, *PINK-1*, and *PRKN*⁷⁸. In addition, over 90 single nucleotide polymorphisms have been combined into a genetic risk score that is associated with increased risk of clinical PD⁸³. Given the low or variable penetrance of many genetic traits associated with NSD, and that many individuals with these variants do not go on to develop evidence for n-asyn, the NSD-ISS does not consider genotype (aside from fully penetrant pathogenic variants in *SNCA*) sufficient to define the disease. However, understanding of the genetics of NSD is of paramount significance, continues to evolve, and we expect the incorporation of genetics into the NSD-ISS to also evolve.

The majority of individuals with risk variants who develop dopamine loss and functional impairment also show n-asyn pathology and meet criteria for NSD. However, a subset of individuals, including some of those with pathogenic *LRRK2* variants or the majority of those with pathogenic *PRKN* variants, have evidence of dopaminergic dysfunction (D+) but do not have evidence of n-asyn^{2,4,84-86} (S-D+G+). In the absence of n-asyn at a given time of assessment, these individuals do not have detectable NSD and must be defined and staged separately (see below).

Overview of the NSD-ISS

NSD is a continuum, but defining discrete stages is required to provide a research framework for therapeutic development from the earliest stages of disease, when pathologic changes are identifiable but there are no clinical manifestations or functional consequences, to advanced disease (Figure 1).

We propose an integrated staging system anchored on the disease biology. The biologic definition of NSD is key to enable staging based on biomarkers in Stages 1 and 2. Stages 3-6 are defined by integrating biomarkers with clinical signs/symptoms and specific anchors for their functional impact (Table 1, Figure 2). While the NSD-ISS stages are sequential, timing of assessments and individual rates of progression may limit practical observation of early stages or sequential progression through subsequent stages.

Individuals with pathogenic variants potentially associated with NSD risk but who do not have evidence for n-asyn are designated as low or high genetic risk (R^L or R^H respectively). They are referenced here to provide a framework within which to conduct research and clinical trials, but these individuals do not have NSD and thus are not assigned a stage.

The NSD-ISS

Stage 0 is defined by the presence of fully penetrant pathogenic variants in genes established to manifest solely with NSD pathology. At present, fully penetrant pathogenic variants in SNCA are the only known genetic cause of NSD that meet this criterion and included in Stage 0. These cases are very rare but important for understanding NSD biology and targeting therapeutic development aiming to ultimately prevent progression to Stage 1 and beyond. If other pathogenic variants that are fully penetrant for NSD pathology are identified, they may be added to the definition of Stage 0. Pathogenic variants in other genes do not define stages but are included, if present, along with S and D status in every stage.

Stage 1 and beyond require detection of n-*asyn* (S+). Stage 1A includes individuals with biomarker evidence of n-*asyn* (S+), without evidence of dopaminergic dysfunction (D-), and no relevant signs/symptoms. Given the rarity of SCNA pathogenic variants, the majority of individuals with NSD will hypothetically “start” in Stage 1. Stage 1B includes individuals with biomarker evidence of n-*asyn* (S+) and dopaminergic dysfunction (D+), but no relevant signs/symptoms or functional abnormalities. We separate Stage 1A versus Stage 1B based on the hypothesis that n-*asyn* precedes onset of dopaminergic dysfunction. Limited but accumulating data support this hypothesis^{2,40}, but more evidence is required.

Stage 2 is defined by the presence of subtle clinical signs/symptoms but without functional impairment. Clinical signs/symptoms may be motor or non-motor. Non-motor signs/symptoms include olfactory dysfunction, dysautonomia (orthostatic hypotension, heart rate abnormalities), constipation, neuropsychiatric symptoms (depression, anxiety), mild cognitive impairment, and disorders of sleep and wakefulness (RBD, excessive daytime sleepiness). Some non-motor symptoms, like anxiety or constipation, may be nonspecific, resulting from processes unrelated to n-*asyn* that are common in aging. The lack of specificity of these clinical features is mitigated by the requirement for n-*asyn* in these individuals, but we recognize that there is some uncertainty in the spectrum of the clinical features advancing individuals from NSD Stage 1 to 2, which requires investigation in future studies.

Similar to Stage 1, Stage 2 is subdivided into 2A and 2B based on presence of biomarkers. Ultimately, progression of biomarkers during Stages 1 and 2 may provide an opportunity to test therapeutics that slow/prevent individuals with evidence of n-*asyn* from developing dopaminergic dysfunction.

Stage 2B and beyond require presence of both biomarkers of n-*asyn* (S+) AND dopaminergic dysfunction (D+). The majority of individuals with n-*asyn* will demonstrate dopaminergic dysfunction at the time of motor, cognitive, or other non-motor functional impairment^{57,63-67}, but additional evidence is required to determine how often functional impairment may occur in NSD with n-*asyn* before dopaminergic dysfunction is detected. Current data suggest this is uncommon, but additional data could warrant modification of the requirement for both (S+) and (D+) to advance to Stage 3. NSD-ISS provides a research framework to systematically address these questions.

In Stages 3-6, the severity of functional impairment defines each progressive stage. Functional impairment can be driven by relevant motor, cognitive, or other non-motor clinical signs/symptoms. While this staging system is grounded on the NSD biological framework, defining the degree of functional impairment using a data-driven approach is necessary for therapeutics development and other applications of the NSD-ISS. We have conceptualized functional impairment qualitatively as progressing along the continuum of *slight, mild, moderate, severe* and provide categorical descriptors of such (Table1).

Most individuals with *newly diagnosed* PD, as defined by current clinical diagnostic criteria²² will be Stage 3, but some without functional impairment will be Stage 2B. This staging based on biology and functional impairment is a major strength of the proposed staging framework, particularly to guide selection of

participants for targeted drug development. Notably, those with a primarily cognitive syndrome and NSD-defining biology will fit in the NSD-ISS based on anchors of cognitive functional impairment.

While operational definitions of anchors for functional impairment for Stage 3-6 are beyond the scope of this conceptual paper, they are critical for future versions of the NSD-ISS. We envision that the field will soon align on these as data emerge. Examples of these anchors will be provided in a separate report to begin a data-driven discussion to develop consensus. Specifically, data derived from motor, non-motor, and cognitive functional rating scales assessments (i.e., ability to perform activities of daily living) in prospective cohort studies and clinical trials will be used to define thresholds for Stages 3-6, akin to the HD-ISS¹⁴. The Movement Disorders Society-Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS)⁸⁷ Parts I and II are widely used to measure functional impairment and may be applied as a starting point. However, MDS-UPDRS has limited sensitivity to detect changes in function in earlier disease stages and likely new scales and approaches need to be developed⁸⁸.

Progression of NSD Stages

NSD is a continuum, and an individual in a given stage is presumed to have passed through all preceding stages beginning with Stage 1A. This is supported by data from prospective observational studies^{2,40,63-67}, though additional data in the earliest stages of NSD are still needed. For example, an individual who is observed to be in Stage 3 at a given point in time is presumed have passed through Stage 1 (first Stage 1A, then 1B) and then Stage 2. However, passage through each of these stages may not have necessarily been observed depending on the timing of assessment. The NSD-ISS framework will enable the studies required to investigate timing for progression from each stage to the next and the key additional biologic determinants that may influence the rate of progression.

Progression from Stage 1 to Stage 6 may not occur in all individuals with NSD and if it occurs, may not be linear. Indeed, it is likely that a significant proportion of individuals in Stage 1A—that is, who are S+ but are entirely asymptomatic—will not go on to develop signs or symptoms and therefore may remain in Stage 1A for life. As with other neurodegenerative diseases including AD^{12,13} and HD¹⁴, a biologic definition of NSD enables detection of asymptomatic disease, which is crucial for the development and testing of therapies that might prevent the progression of NSD biology before any clinically-meaningful consequences arise. We recognize that there may be important psychosocial and economic consequences to such early identification of neurodegenerative diseases that require further study. The NSD-ISS research framework will enable systematic evaluation to optimize the process of providing these results to research participants.

Biologically-Defined NSD Encompasses PD, DLB, RBD and other Clinical Syndromes

The core principle of the NSD-ISS is that NSD is defined by biology. Yet, a disease based on a single biology may have protean clinical manifestations. As such, individuals with NSD may have a range of clinical syndromes (Table 2). In most cases these syndromes will overlap, and contributions from motor and non-motor features will produce a cumulative impact on functional impairment. Clinical syndromes arising from NSD include n-*syn*-driven motor parkinsonism and cognitive syndromes—currently diagnosed as PD, PDD, or DLB based on clinical diagnostic criteria²²⁻²⁴. Other well described syndromes include RBD⁸⁹ and dysautonomia (including PAF)⁹⁰; neuropsychiatric symptoms may predominate as well^{19,21}. While the NSD-ISS provides unifying biological definition and staging, recognition of clinical syndromes is essentially important to guide syndrome-focused symptomatic management, family support, and education.

Another important implication of the biologically-based framework of the NSD-ISS is that *a clinical diagnosis of prodromal PD, or clinically defined PD, PDD, or DLB is neither sufficient nor necessary for*

a NSD diagnosis. The NSD-ISS unifies what is currently defined as prodromal PD and DLB¹⁹⁻²¹ and related disorders along the same continuum of progression of the NSD neurodegenerative process (Figure 1). The current distinction of prodromal versus clinically-diagnosed PD or DLB is artificial, lacks standardized criteria for transition and creates barriers in therapeutic development. Terminology such as “phenoconversion” lacks operational definition and is faulted by subjectivity. Enrolling individuals with NSD in Stages 1 and 2 (previously termed “prodromal populations”) into trials testing experimental therapeutics targeting specific molecular pathways is of high interest^{7,8}. Success of these clinical trials depends on identifying participants with a unifying underlying disease biology and establishing the framework for defining progression. A biologic definition and integrated staging system aim to accomplish both goals.

Incorporating other pathologies into the NSD-ISS framework

Many individuals have mixed pathology and comorbid diseases in addition to NSD. A key challenge for the NSD-ISS will be to assess the relative impact of clinical signs/symptoms, particularly cognitive, on functional impairment in individuals with multiple underlying pathophysiological processes and variable clinical syndromes. The NSD-ISS enables investigation of the biologic mechanisms resulting in functional impairment and incorporation of biomarkers of AD pathology and other conditions into NSD staging.

Individuals who do not have NSD

Based on extensive data from multiple cohorts^{2-4,6} the biologic definition of NSD applies to the majority (>90%) of individuals diagnosed with PD and DLB as per current clinical diagnostic criteria. By defining the disease based on biology, and specifically by the presence of n-asyn, application of the NSD-ISS may result in the identification of individuals with parkinsonism and evidence of dopaminergic dysfunction (D+)² who are n-asyn negative (S-). These individuals do not have NSD, regardless of their clinical syndrome, even in the presence of evidence of dopaminergic dysfunction or pathogenic genetic variants, and staging by NSD-ISS does not apply to them. While determining the etiology of parkinsonism in such individuals is critical, it is beyond the scope of this work; S- status does not inform alternate diagnoses but highlights specific examples of relevance to therapeutic development and the need for further research as elaborated below.

S-D+G- (Multiple System Atrophy)

NSD does not include MSA. MSA is an alpha-synucleinopathy marked by predominantly glial asyn accumulation^{30,91}. Several lines of evidence support the notion that there are different asyn ‘strains’ in MSA and NSD^{41,91,92}. For example, cryogenic electron microscopy studies have demonstrated different conformations of asyn filaments derived from brains of individuals with MSA vs NSD¹⁸. Critically, advances in the most widely-applied CSF asyn SAA enable the distinction between n-asyn and glial-predominant asyn forms associated with MSA, based on different maximum fluorescence emitted during amplification^{41,42,44,45}.

S-D+G- (Other known biologies)

Other individuals with dopamine dysfunction without n-asyn also do not have NSD but may have other known biologies (Table 3). Examples include progressive supranuclear palsy (PSP) and corticobasal degeneration caused by tau- or TDP-related neurodegeneration⁹³.

S-D+G+

There are subsets of individuals with genetic variants (G+) such as in *LRRK2* or *PRKN* with evidence of dopaminergic dysfunction (D+) and parkinsonism but without evidence of n-asyn (S-), whether assessed by CSF asyn SAA or on neuropathological examination^{2-4,84-86,94,95}. These S-D+G+ individuals do not have NSD (Table 3). Elucidating the pathology in these individuals is a research priority. This biologic heterogeneity is only evident when the disease is defined by its biology and highlights the value of biologic rather than clinical disease definition. Understanding the biology of S-D+G+ will inform and improve clinical trial design. The NSD-ISS provides the framework for determining whether a given therapeutic strategy is appropriate for specific populations of individuals with neurodegeneration or at risk for it, determined based on knowledge of the mechanism of action and inclusion of biomarker-defined groups in study samples. For example, *LRRK2*+ S- participants may be included in *LRRK2*-targeted therapeutic studies independent of their S status⁹⁶ but would not be candidates for n-asyn-targeting therapeutic studies.

S-D+G- with unknown biology

Among individuals with clinically diagnosed sporadic PD and with evidence of dopaminergic dysfunction, 6.7% do not have n-asyn, relevant genetic variants, or alternative known biology² (S-D+G-) (Table 3). While the performance characteristics of the CSF asyn SAA as well as neuropathological studies⁹⁷ indicate these cases are truly n-asyn negative, additional studies in larger population-based cohorts are needed to confirm this. These individuals do not meet the biologic definition for NSD. Further studies will elucidate the relevant biologies underlying the neurodegenerative process in these individuals. Importantly, these individuals should not be enrolled into asyn-targeting therapeutic trials, again highlighting the importance of accurate biological definition.

Applications of the NSD-ISS

This first iteration of the NSD-ISS is intended to provide a research framework to accelerate therapeutic development, similar to the evolution of disease definition and staging of AD^{12,13}. Indeed, at present, application of the NSD-ISS in the clinical setting is premature. It is inappropriate to use the NSD-ISS clinically before sufficient data are available to enable understanding of stage dependent disease progression. Nevertheless, the ultimate goal is advancement of knowledge to the point where a clinically-useful staging system is available, to aid in early, accurate diagnosis and to guide treatment.

During the process of development of the NSD-ISS (appendix page 1), there was broad consensus from key stakeholders¹⁵ that its adoption would allow the field to accelerate and improve therapeutic development at all disease stages, from prior to onset of signs/symptoms through mild to severe functional impairment. Identifying individuals based on biologic characteristics enables a new approach to developing therapies targeting relevant biology and testing therapeutic strategies that will pave the way for precision medicine in the treatment of NSD^{8,98}.

The NSD-ISS, with a consistent and uniformly understood definition of the study sample at each stage, provides a framework and clearly-defined roadmap for clinical trial design and evaluation by key constituencies, including pharmaceutical drug developers, regulators, academic experts and clinical trial participants. It also enables development of stage-dependent outcomes to allow assessment within a stage and to define changes between stages⁹⁸ (e.g., outcomes could reflect change from Stage 2B to Stage 3 or ultimately from Stage 1 to Stage 2). In turn, the availability of stage-appropriate endpoints can facilitate therapeutic development, including symptomatic therapies for individuals in late stages of the disease. Importantly it also ensures that individual who do not have n-asyn pathology are not enrolled and subjected to the risk and burden of n-asyn targeted therapeutic interventions.

A major advantage of the NSD-ISS will be to reduce heterogeneity in clinical trials by requiring biologic consistency within the study sample rather than identifying study participants based on clinical criteria for PD and DLB, which introduces wide variability. In addition, the NSD-ISS provides a framework for designing studies to answer several crucial outstanding questions related to the epidemiology of NSD, including the prevalence of asymptomatic n-asyn in the general population (i.e., prevalence of Stage 1), incidence of n-asyn positivity in different populations, and temporal progression across stages, including importantly from S+D- to S+D+.

Gaps in Knowledge and Future Directions

While current data strongly support the biologic definition for NSD and the NSD-ISS, we recognize that there are knowledge gaps and that our understanding of NSD biology and staging will evolve. These gaps, in turn, define key research priorities for the field. *Importantly, the NSD-ISS provides a framework within which to answer key outstanding research questions, which will inform future iterations of the staging system.*

- While CSF asyn SAA is a validated biomarker of n-asyn, it requires CSF collection and currently the assay is available in a limited number of qualified labs. Thus, more feasible and scalable measures for n-asyn are required.
- Additional data on n-asyn is needed in diverse samples representative of the general population, on a greater number of disease populations including larger samples of research participants with clinical diagnosis of DLB, and in the real-world setting. This will be enabled by more scalable and feasible matrices for n-asyn assessment.
- The S and D domains are currently categorical. There is a crucial need for quantitative biomarkers to measure disease onset, progression, and response to therapy.
- Development of biomarkers that are feasible, minimally invasive and cost effective will facilitate inclusive and representative population screening.
- The timeline of progression along the axis of biological staging is unknown. The prevalence of n-asyn in asymptomatic older adults is age-dependent and is estimated at 5-12%^{2,6,27,39,99}. These individuals have NSD as defined here. Studies are needed to better understand the epidemiology of these Stage 1A individuals, including the incidence of and rate of progression to D+, and incident functional impairment. Such data will be essential to enable therapeutic development for true prevention of disability.
- Understanding the biology of research participants with clinically diagnosed PD or DLB who do not have NSD (S-D+G+ and S-D+G- individuals) is a high priority.
- As reliable biomarkers emerge that reflect molecular changes of underlying mechanisms of neurodegeneration (i.e., mitochondrial, lysosomal, inflammatory, and other pathways³⁰) that are NSD-specific, additional biologic anchors will be introduced to refine the staging system.
- NSD is a multisystem disease that involves neurodegeneration in other neurotransmitter systems besides dopamine⁷⁶. With validation of biomarkers that reflect pathology in these systems will come the opportunities to incorporate them.
- Defining specific functional anchors across stages 3-6 was outside of the scope of this conceptual paper and is underway. Several observational cohort studies, including PPMI⁷⁰, DLB consortium¹⁰⁰, and clinical trials⁷¹ offer critical data that will allow validation of such anchors.
- Current understanding of the clinical features of NSD, especially in its earliest stages, is largely based on prospective cohort studies of population-based samples and samples recruited based on genetic risk or presence of non-motor features seen prior to diagnosis^{19,20}. With the biologic definition of NSD now comes the opportunity to study biomarker-defined cohorts and prospectively observe the evolution of non-motor and motor features in a manner that allows establishment of specificity for underlying biology. As additional data emerge, Stage 2 of the NSD-

ISS may be modified to incorporate relative weights of different clinical features according to their specificity for underlying etiology.

- A key challenge for the NSD-ISS will be to assess degree of contribution of multiple co-pathologies on clinical functional impairment (particularly cognitive impairment). Ultimately, acquiring AD and other neurodegenerative biomarkers may become a routine component of NSD staging.

Conclusion

We propose a biological definition and a research framework for an integrated staging system for NSD. The strength of NSD-ISS is that it is based on a biological definition of disease and integrates biology and progressive functional impairment. Starting with homogeneous biology enables both the investigation of all clinical syndromes encompassed by NSD and encourages the development of stage-specific outcomes to further assess disease progression and therapeutic intervention.

The NSD-ISS will enhance trial efficiency, provide a consistent and uniformly understood definition for the study sample at each stage, and enable selection of appropriate trial endpoints. The NSD-ISS will evolve as new data and biomarkers emerge. Presently, NSD-ISS is intended for research use only; its application in the clinical setting is premature and inappropriate.

Panel. Glossary of terms

Term	Abbreviation	Definition
Neuronal alpha-synuclein	n-asyn	Disease-defining form of asyn: misfolded, pathological predominantly neuronal alpha-synuclein
Neuronal alpha-synuclein disease	NSD	Disease defined by presence of n-asyn and ultimately dopaminergic dysfunction. Disease is defined independent of presence of clinical signs and symptoms
S anchor for NSD	S	Indicates presence (S+) or absence (S-) of n-asyn as measured by any validated biomarker of n-asyn pathology
D anchor for NSD	D	Indicates presence (D+) or absence (D-) of dopaminergic dysfunction as measured by any validated biomarker of dopaminergic dysfunction
Genetic status	G	Indicates presence (G+) or absence (G-) of relevant pathogenic variants

Figure 1: Hypothetical framework of Neuronal alpha-Synuclein Disease Integrated Staging System. Shapes and slopes of the curves and their temporal relationship are qualitative and hypothetical

Figure 2: Cumulative Staging Framework of the Neuronal alpha-Synuclein Disease Integrated Staging System

Web Appendix Page 1.

Neuronal alpha-Synuclein Disease definition and staging development: methods and process

* CP: Cure Parkinson's; CPP: Critical Path for Parkinson's Consortium; LBDA: Lewy Body Dementia Association; MDS: International Parkinson and Movement Disorder Society; MHRA: Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency; MJFF: The Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research; PC: Parkinson Canada; PF: Parkinson's Foundation; PUK: Parkinson's UK; SIUFA: Shake It Up Australia Foundation.

Table 1: Neuronal alpha-Synuclein Disease: an Integrated Staging System

Disease Continuum	Stage	Stage Definition	aSyn Biomarker (S)	Dopamine Dysfunction Biomarker (D)	Clinical Signs and Symptoms Attributable to PD, DLB and other NSD syndromes	Functional Impairment Attributable to PD, DLB and other NSD syndromes
Genetic risk	R ^L	(G) Genetic risk variants – Low age adjusted risk (constantly redefined).	-	-	No clinical signs or symptoms	No functional impairment
Genetic risk	R ^H	(G) Genetic risk variants – High age adjusted risk (constantly redefined)	-	-	No clinical signs or symptoms	No functional impairment
NSD	0	(G) Fully penetrant <i>SNCA</i> variant	-	-	No clinical signs or symptoms	No functional impairment
NSD	1A	Characteristic pathological changes but no evidence of clinical signs or symptoms	+	-	No clinical signs or symptoms	No functional impairment
NSD	1B	Characteristic pathologic changes plus dopaminergic dysfunction but no evidence of clinical signs or symptoms	+	+	No clinical signs or symptoms	No functional impairment
NSD	2A	Characteristic pathological changes and subtle detectable clinical signs and symptoms but no functional impairment.	+	-	Subtle clinical signs or symptoms. Can be motor or non-motor: hyposmia, RBD, cognitive abnormalities, constipation, dysautonomia, depression, anxiety.	No functional impairment
NSD	2B	Characteristic pathologic changes plus dopaminergic dysfunction and subtle detectable clinical signs and symptoms but no functional impairment.	+	+	<i>Same as Stage 2A</i>	No functional impairment
NSD	3	Characteristic pathologic changes plus dopaminergic dysfunction and clinical signs and symptoms causing slight functional impairment.	+	+	Relevant motor and non-motor signs and symptoms increasing in severity, but stage is defined by the degree of functional impairment	Slight: Functional impairment with minimal impact on complex tasks of daily life and usual activities, such as: finances, transportation, food, household, conversation
NSD	4	Characteristic pathologic changes plus dopaminergic dysfunction and clinical signs and symptoms causing mild functional impairment.	+	+	<i>See entry for Stage 3</i>	Mild: Functional impairment severe enough to cause some impairment in complex tasks of daily life and usual activities, but basic tasks of daily life related to personal care are intact, such as: bathing, dressing, walking, using the toilet, eating
NSD	5	Characteristic pathologic changes plus dopaminergic dysfunction and clinical signs and symptoms causing moderate functional impairment.	+	+	<i>See entry for Stage 3</i>	Moderate: Functional impairment severe enough to require assistance with basic tasks of daily life
NSD	6	Characteristic pathologic changes plus dopaminergic dysfunction and clinical signs and symptoms causing severe functional impairment	+	+	<i>See entry for Stage 3</i>	Severe: Functional impairment severe enough to require dependence on others for basic tasks of daily life

Table 2: Neuronal alpha-Synuclein Disease diagnosis: spectrum of clinical syndromes

NSD diagnosis	NSD clinical syndromes*
NSD is defined by biology. Clinical entities represent a spectrum of the clinical syndromes under the biological of NSD	NSD. Motor syndrome (i.e., Parkinson’s syndrome)
	NSD. Cognitive syndrome (i.e., DLB syndrome, Parkinson’s syndrome)
	NSD. Neuropsychiatric syndrome (i.e., disease-relevant anxiety, depression)
	NSD. Sleep disorder syndrome (i.e., RBD)
	NSD. Other non-motor syndromes (i.e., autonomic, hyposmia)

*Majority of individuals will have a combination of multiple and overlapping syndromes but may have initial clinical presentation within a particular domain

Table 3: Biological/ clinical categories that are not Neuronal alpha-Synuclein Disease

Biomarker Profile			Designation
S	D	G	
-	+	NA	Dopaminergic dysfunction with motor or cognitive functional impairment with predominantly glial asyn (i.e., MSA)
-	+	NA	Dopaminergic dysfunction with motor or cognitive functional impairment without n-asyn-known biology (i.e., PSP, CBD)
-	+	+	Genetic variants with dopaminergic dysfunction but without evidence of n-asyn
-	+	-	Dopaminergic dysfunction with motor or cognitive functional impairment without n-asyn and without known genetic variant- unknown biology
-	-	-	Motor or cognitive functional impairment but without n-asyn, dopaminergic dysfunction, known biology or relevant genetic variants

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

This article reflects the views of the authors and should not be construed to represent FDA's views or policies.

TSi declares consultancies for 4D Pharma, Acadia, AcureX, AskBio, Amneal, Blue Rock Therapeutics, Caraway, Critical Path for Parkinson's Consortium, Denali, The Michael J. Fox Foundation, Neuroderm, Roche, Sanofi, Sinopia, Sunovion, Takeda, UCB, Vanqua Bio, and Voyager. LC declares research support and consulting fees from The Michael J. Fox Foundation. KP declares consultancies for Curasen; was on a scientific advisory board for Curasen and Amprion; honoraria from invited scientific presentations to universities and professional societies not exceeding \$5000 per year from California Congress of Clinical Neurology, California Neurological Society, and Johns Hopkins University; and patents or patent applications numbers 17/314,979 and 63/377,293. KP also declares grants to her institution (Stanford University School of Medicine) from NIH/NINDS NS115114, NS062684, NS075097, NIH/NIA U19 AG065156, P30 AG066515, The Michael J. Fox Foundation, Lewy Body Dementia Association, Alzheimer's Drug Discovery Foundation, Sue Berghoff LBD Research Fellowship and the Knight Initiative for Brain Resilience. MB declares travel grants from The Michael J. Fox Foundation. TB has no declarations. MC has no declarations. SC declares employment for and travel grants from The Michael J. Fox Foundation. The Michael J. Fox Foundation received funding support from named nonprofit institutions (Cure Parkinson's, Lewy Body Dementia Association, Parkinson Canada, Parkinson's UK, Shake It Up Australia Foundation) to convene an in-person roundtable of experts in April 2023 in which The Michael J. Fox Foundation (employer) cost-shared; The Michael J. Fox Foundation (employer) provided funding for an in-person meeting in January 2023. CC declares grants from The Michael J. Fox Foundation and NIH/NINDS. LC-M declares employment for and employee stock options in Amprion, grants from The Michael J. Fox Foundation and patents or patent application numbers US 20210277076A1, US 20210311077A1, US 20190353669A1 and US 20210223268A1. TD declares former employment of and may hold stock/stock options in Biogen. PD has no declarations. TF declares travel grants and grant payments to her institution (Indiana University) from The Michael J. Fox Foundation. MF declares employment for The Michael J. Fox Foundation and an unpaid advisory role at Vaxxinity. CG declares research funding to her institution from The Michael J. Fox Foundation. DJ declares employment for and employee stock options from Denali Therapeutics. KK declares support to his institution (University of Rochester Medical Center) from The Michael J. Fox Foundation. CK declares employment for and travel grants from The Michael J. Fox Foundation. The Michael J. Fox Foundation received funding support from named nonprofit institutions (Cure Parkinson's, Lewy Body Dementia Association, Parkinson Canada, Parkinson's UK, Shake It Up Australia Foundation) to convene an in-person roundtable of experts in April 2023 in which The Michael J. Fox Foundation (employer) cost-shared; The Michael J. Fox Foundation (employer) provided funding for an in-person meeting in January 2023. KMe declares consultancies for The Michael J. Fox Foundation, AcuRx, Caraway, Cerebral Therapeutics, NRG Therapeutics (scientific advisory board), Nitrase Therapeutics (scientific advisory board), Nurabio, Retromer Therapeutics (director on the board, part-time chief scientific officer), Schrodinger, Sinopia Biosciences (scientific advisory board), and Vanqua Biosciences (scientific advisory board); stock ownership for Cognition Therapeutics, Eli Lilly (retiree stock holder), Envisagenics, Nitrase Therapeutics, Sinopia Biosciences and Retromer Therapeutics; honoraria for the University of Utah; patents or patent applications for Retromer Therapeutics (planned patent); research grant from The Michael J. Fox Foundation and travel grants from the University of Utah. BM declares consultancies from Roche, Biogen, and The Michael J. Fox Foundation; grants from The Michael J. Fox Foundation, ASAP and DFG; honoraria for Abbvie; and travel grants for Abbvie. TM declares support to his institution (Stanford University School of Medicine) from The Michael J. Fox Foundation. KN declares support (Patient Council, The Michael J. Fox Foundation) from the Michael J. Fox Foundation. GP declares employment for F. Hoffmann-La Roche Ltd. and stock ownership for F. Hoffmann-La Roche Ltd., Atea, Novartis and Eli Lilly. JS declares consultancies from Invicro, Biogen, and Abbvie; and stock ownership from RealmIDX, MNI Holdings, and LikeMinds as well as grants from The

Michael J. Fox Foundation. TSh declares employment for The Michael J. Fox Foundation. ASin declares employment for The National Institutes of Health who received grants from The Michael J. Fox Foundation and ASAP. ASin declares Diagnostic for Stroke royalties (unrelated to current work); honoraria from Movement Disorders Society and Nature Publishing Group; travel grants from Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, The Michael J. Fox Foundation and Weill Cornell. ASin's spouse is an employee of GeneDx. DS has no declarations. MS declared consultancies for Mediflix, Inc., Health and Wellness Partners; honoraria from Atria Foundation, International Parkinson and Movement Disorder Society, Neurocrine, Luye Pharma and Acorda. MS serves on advisory board at Neuroderm, Alexza, Alexion and Biogen. CS declares employment for Amprion; stock ownership for Amprion; honoraria (will receive royalties for the sale of seed amplification assay [SAA]) from Amprion; and patents or patent applications, awarded and amplified in conjunction with Amprion for the SAA assay. CT declares consultancies for CNS Ratings, Australian Parkinson's Mission, Biogen, Evidera, Cadent (data safety monitoring board), Adamas (steering committee), Biogen (via the Parkinson Study Group steering committee), Kyowa Kirin (advisory board), Lundbeck (advisory board), Jazz/Cavion (steering committee), Acorda (advisory board), Bial (DMC) and Genentech. CT also declares grant support to UCSF from The Michael J. Fox Foundation, National Institute of Health, Gateway LLC, Department of Defense, Roche Genentech, Biogen, Parkinson Foundation and Marcus Program in Precision Medicine. ET has no declarations. DW declares salary support from The Michael J. Fox Foundation for serving on an Executive Steering Committee for the PPMI. YX declares employment for and travel grants from The Michael J. Fox Foundation. The Michael J. Fox Foundation received funding support from named nonprofit institutions (Cure Parkinson's, Lewy Body Dementia Association, Parkinson Canada, Parkinson's UK, Shake It Up Australia Foundation) to convene an in-person roundtable of experts in April 2023 in which The Michael J. Fox Foundation (employer) cost-shared; The Michael J. Fox Foundation (employer) provided funding for an in-person meeting in January 2023. ASid declares consultancies for SPARC Therapeutics, Capsida Therapeutics and Parkinson Study Group; honoraria from Bial; grants from The Michael J. Fox Foundation (member of PPMI Steering Committee) and National Institutes of Health; and participation on board at Wave Life Sciences, Inhibikase, Preval and Huntington Study Group and Massachusetts General Hospital. BD has received consulting fees and travel support for his role as an advisor for Arch Venture Partners, Cerveau Technologies, Epilepsy Foundation, F-PRIME Capital, Loulou Foundation and The Michael J. Fox Foundation. BD has a leadership or fiduciary role in the Virginia Neurological Society (past president) and Prothena Inc. (Director). BD holds stock options with Prothena Inc. KM declares support to his institution (Institute for Neurodegenerative Disorders) from The Michael J. Fox Foundation. KMa also declares consultancies for Invicro, The Michael J. Fox Foundation, Roche, Calico, Coave, Neuron23, Orbimed, Biohaven, Anofi, Koneksa, Merck, Lilly, Inhibikase, Neuramedy, IRLabs and Prothena. KMa participates on DSMB at Biohaven.

Contributors and Author Roles

TSi, LC, KP, SC, LC-M, TD, TB, CC, PD, TF, MF, DJ, KK, CK, KMe, BM, TM, KN, GP, JS, TSh, ASin, DS, MS, CS, CT, ET, DW, YX, ASid, WP, BD and KMa contributed to the conceptualization. TSi, LC, MB, CC, CG, ASid, WP, BD and KMa contributed to the data curation and formal analysis. TSi, LC, MB, CC, ASid, WP, BD and KMa contributed to the validation. TSi, LC, KP, LC-M, TD, PD, TF, CG, DJ, KK, KMe, BM, TM, KN, GP, JS, ASin, DS, MS, CS, CT, ET, DW, ASid, WP, BD and KMa contributed to the supervision. TSi, LC, ASid, WP, BD and KMa contributed to the writing of the original draft. SC, MF, CK, TSh and YX acquired funding, provided resources and contributed to the project administration. All authors contributed to the investigations, methodology and the review and editing of the final version of the manuscript. TSi and LMC have had direct access to and verified all components of the submitted manuscript.

Sources of funding:

Funding support for the January 2023 conference was provided by The Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research (MJFF). Funding support for the subsequent April 2023 in-person roundtable and virtual summit was provided by Cure Parkinson's, Lewy Body Dementia Association, MJFF, Parkinson Canada, Parkinson's UK, and Shake It Up Foundation Australia.

Role of the funding source:

Research officers (SC, MF, CK, TS, YX) at The Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research were involved in design of NSD-ISS and writing of the manuscript. Representatives from other funding partners contributed critical review and commentary on concepts and evolution of overarching themes within the NSD-ISS as well as on the pre-publication manuscript.

Acknowledgements:

We appreciate Dr Werner Poewe substantial contribution to the conceptual design of the paper and critical review of the final draft of the manuscript. We are grateful to research advocates Dr. Alison Handler, Dr. Soania Mathur, and Carroll Siu who contributed their perspectives as individuals affected by Parkinson's. We thank representatives from non-profit funders and patient advocates for their strategic support in convening diverse stakeholders and experts to provide input through key meetings and public comment including Angelica Asis, Clyde Campbell, Dr. David Dexter, Dr. Keith N. Fargo, Dr. Karen Lee, Helen Matthews, Dr. Anna Naito, Angela Taylor, and multiple collaborators at the Critical Path Institute.

We also appreciate that while this report presents a conceptual framework for NSD-ISS, the data that has enabled these concepts has largely emerged from the PPMI study. We acknowledge that PPMI is scientifically supported and largely funded by the Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research and Aligning Science Across Parkinson's and the PPMI Partners Scientific Advisory Board (<https://www.ppmi-info.org/about-ppmi/who-we-are/study-sponsors>).

References

1. Fairfoul G, McGuire LI, Pal S, et al. Alpha-synuclein RT-QuIC in the CSF of patients with alpha-synucleinopathies. *Annals of clinical and translational neurology* 2016; **3**(10): 812-8.
2. Siderowf A, Concha-Marambio L, Lafontant D-E, et al. Assessment of heterogeneity and disease onset in the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) cohort using the α -synuclein seed amplification assay: a cross-sectional study. *Lancet Neurol* 2023; **22**(5): 407-17.
3. Bellomo G, De Luca CMG, Paoletti FP, Gaetani L, Moda F, Parnetti L. α -Synuclein Seed Amplification Assays for Diagnosing Synucleinopathies: The Way Forward. *Neurology* 2022; **99**(5): 195-205.
4. Brockmann K, Quadalti C, Lerche S, et al. Association between CSF alpha-synuclein seeding activity and genetic status in Parkinson's disease and dementia with Lewy bodies. *Acta Neuropathol Commun* 2021; **9**(1): 175.
5. Rossi M, Candelise N, Baiardi S, et al. Ultrasensitive RT-QuIC assay with high sensitivity and specificity for Lewy body-associated synucleinopathies. *Acta Neuropathol* 2020; **140**(1): 49-62.
6. Grossauer A, Hemicker G, Krismer F, et al. α -Synuclein Seed Amplification Assays in the Diagnosis of Synucleinopathies Using Cerebrospinal Fluid-A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Mov Disord Clin Pract* 2023; **10**(5): 737-47.
7. Sardi SP, Cedarbaum JM, Brundin P. Targeted Therapies for Parkinson's Disease: From Genetics to the Clinic. *Mov Disord* 2018; **33**(5): 684-96.
8. Berg D, Crotty GF, Keavney JL, Schwarzschild MA, Simuni T, Tanner C. Path to Parkinson Disease Prevention: Conclusion and Outlook. *Neurology* 2022; **99**(7 Supplement 1): 76-83.
9. Mestre TA, Fereshtehnejad SM, Berg D, et al. Parkinson's Disease Subtypes: Critical Appraisal and Recommendations. *J Parkinsons Dis* 2021; **11**(2): 395-404.
10. Parkinson J. An essay on the shaking palsy. 1817. *J Neuropsychiatry Clin Neurosci* 2002; **14**(2): 223-36; discussion 2.
11. McKeith IG, Galasko D, Kosaka K, et al. Consensus guidelines for the clinical and pathologic diagnosis of dementia with Lewy bodies (DLB): report of the consortium on DLB international workshop. *Neurology* 1996; **47**(5): 1113-24.
12. Jack CR, Jr., Bennett DA, Blennow K, et al. NIA-AA Research Framework: Toward a biological definition of Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimers Dement* 2018; **14**(4): 535-62.
13. NIA-AA Revised Clinical Criteria for Alzheimer's Disease. 2023. <https://aaic.alz.org/downloads2023/NIA-AA-Revised-Clinical-Criteria-AAIC-2023.pdf> (accessed August 9 2023).
14. Tabrizi SJ, Schobel S, Gantman EC, et al. A biological classification of Huntington's disease: the Integrated Staging System. *Lancet Neurol* 2022; **21**(7): 632-44.
15. O'Hanlon CE, Farmer CM, Ryan J, Ernecoff N. Clinical Outcome Assessments and Digital Health Technologies Supporting Clinical Trial Endpoints in Early Parkinson's Disease: Roundtable Proceedings and Roadmap for Research. Santa Monica, CA: RAND Corporation; 2023.
16. Guerrero-Ferreira R, Taylor NM, Mona D, et al. Cryo-EM structure of alpha-synuclein fibrils. *Elife* 2018; **7**.
17. Guerrero-Ferreira R, Kovacic L, Ni D, Stahlberg H. New insights on the structure of alpha-synuclein fibrils using cryo-electron microscopy. *Curr Opin Neurobiol* 2020; **61**: 89-95.
18. Yang Y, Shi Y, Schweighauser M, et al. Structures of α -synuclein filaments from human brains with Lewy pathology. *Nature* 2022; **610**(7933): 791-5.
19. Berg D, Postuma RB, Adler CH, et al. MDS research criteria for prodromal Parkinson's disease. *Movement disorders : official journal of the Movement Disorder Society* 2015; **30**(12): 1600-11.
20. Heinzl S, Berg D, Gasser T, et al. Update of the MDS research criteria for prodromal Parkinson's disease. *Mov Disord* 2019; **34**(10): 1464-70.
21. McKeith IG, Ferman TJ, Thomas AJ, et al. Research criteria for the diagnosis of prodromal dementia with Lewy bodies. *Neurology* 2020; **94**(17): 743-55.

22. Postuma RB, Berg D, Stern M, et al. MDS clinical diagnostic criteria for Parkinson's disease. *Movement disorders : official journal of the Movement Disorder Society* 2015; **30**(12): 1591-601.
23. McKeith IG, Boeve BF, Dickson DW, et al. Diagnosis and management of dementia with Lewy bodies: Fourth consensus report of the DLB Consortium. *Neurology* 2017; **89**(1): 88-100.
24. Emre M, Aarsland D, Brown R, et al. Clinical diagnostic criteria for dementia associated with Parkinson's disease. *Movement disorders : official journal of the Movement Disorder Society* 2007; **22**(12): 1689-707.
25. Siderowf A, Stern MB. Preclinical diagnosis of Parkinson's disease: are we there yet? *Current neurology and neuroscience reports* 2006; **6**(4): 295-301.
26. Ross GW, Abbott RD, Petrovitch H, Tanner CM, White LR. Pre-motor features of Parkinson's disease: the Honolulu-Asia Aging Study experience. *Parkinsonism & related disorders* 2012; **18 Suppl 1**: S199-202.
27. Koeglsperger T, Rumpf SL, Schließer P, et al. Neuropathology of incidental Lewy body & prodromal Parkinson's disease. *Mol Neurodegener* 2023; **18**(1): 32.
28. Goedert M, Spillantini MG, Del Tredici K, Braak H. 100 years of Lewy pathology. *Nature Reviews Neurology* 2013; **9**(1): 13-24.
29. Spillantini MG, Schmidt ML, Lee VM, Trojanowski JQ, Jakes R, Goedert M. Alpha-synuclein in Lewy bodies. *Nature* 1997; **388**(6645): 839-40.
30. Calabresi P, Mechelli A, Natale G, Volpicelli-Daley L, Di Lazzaro G, Ghiglieri V. Alpha-synuclein in Parkinson's disease and other synucleinopathies: from overt neurodegeneration back to early synaptic dysfunction. *Cell Death Dis* 2023; **14**(3): 176.
31. Magalhães P, Lashuel HA. Opportunities and challenges of alpha-synuclein as a potential biomarker for Parkinson's disease and other synucleinopathies. *NPJ Parkinsons Dis* 2022; **8**(1): 93.
32. Höglinger GU, Adler CH, Berg D, et al. Towards a Biological Definition of Parkinson's Disease. Preprints: Preprints; 2023.
33. Russo MJ, Orru CD, Concha-Marambio L, et al. High diagnostic performance of independent alpha-synuclein seed amplification assays for detection of early Parkinson's disease. *Acta Neuropathol Commun* 2021; **9**(1): 179.
34. Kang UJ, Boehme AK, Fairfoul G, et al. Comparative study of cerebrospinal fluid α -synuclein seeding aggregation assays for diagnosis of Parkinson's disease. *Mov Disord* 2019; **34**(4): 536-44.
35. Bargar C, Wang W, Gunzler SA, et al. Streamlined alpha-synuclein RT-QuIC assay for various biospecimens in Parkinson's disease and dementia with Lewy bodies. *Acta Neuropathol Commun* 2021; **9**(1): 62.
36. Singer W, Schmeichel AM, Shahnawaz M, et al. Alpha-Synuclein Oligomers and Neurofilament Light Chain Predict Phenoconversion of Pure Autonomic Failure. *Ann Neurol* 2021; **89**(6): 1212-20.
37. Concha-Marambio L, Farris CM, Holguin B, et al. Seed Amplification Assay to Diagnose Early Parkinson's and Predict Dopaminergic Deficit Progression. *Mov Disord* 2021; **36**(10): 2444-6.
38. Iranzo A, Fairfoul G, Ayudhaya ACN, et al. Detection of α -synuclein in CSF by RT-QuIC in patients with isolated rapid-eye-movement sleep behaviour disorder: a longitudinal observational study. *Lancet Neurol* 2021; **20**(3): 203-12.
39. Palmqvist S, Rossi M, Hall S, et al. Cognitive effects of Lewy body pathology in clinically unimpaired individuals. *Nat Med* 2023.
40. Marek KR, D; Concha, L; Choi, C; Jennings, D; Brumm, M; Coffey, C; Brown, E; Stern, M; Seibyl, J; Soto, C; Siderowf, A; PARS Investigators;. Widespread synuclein pathology in hyposmics precedes dopamine transporter deficit in PARS. International Congress of Parkinson's Disease and Movement Disorders August 2023; Copenhagen, Denmark.
41. Shahnawaz M, Mukherjee A, Pritzkow S, et al. Discriminating α -synuclein strains in Parkinson's disease and multiple system atrophy. *Nature* 2020; **578**(7794): 273-7.
42. Singer W, Schmeichel AM, Shahnawaz M, et al. Alpha-Synuclein Oligomers and Neurofilament Light Chain in Spinal Fluid Differentiate Multiple System Atrophy from Lewy Body Synucleinopathies. *Ann Neurol* 2020; **88**(3): 503-12.

43. Mollenhauer B, Batrla R, El-Agnaf O, et al. A user's guide for alpha-synuclein biomarker studies in biological fluids: Perianalytical considerations. *Movement disorders : official journal of the Movement Disorder Society* 2017; **32**(8): 1117-30.
44. Concha-Marambio L, Pritzkow S, Shahnawaz M, Farris CM, Soto C. Seed amplification assay for the detection of pathologic alpha-synuclein aggregates in cerebrospinal fluid. *Nat Protoc* 2023; **18**(4): 1179-96.
45. Okuzumi A, Hatano T, Matsumoto G, et al. Propagative α -synuclein seeds as serum biomarkers for synucleinopathies. *Nature Medicine* 2023.
46. Gibbons C, Wang N, Rajan S, et al. Cutaneous α -Synuclein Signatures in Patients With Multiple System Atrophy and Parkinson Disease. *Neurology* 2023; **100**(15): e1529-e39.
47. Kluge A, Bunk J, Schaeffer E, et al. Detection of neuron-derived pathological α -synuclein in blood. *Brain* 2022; **145**(9): 3058-71.
48. Doppler K. Detection of Dermal Alpha-Synuclein Deposits as a Biomarker for Parkinson's Disease. *J Parkinsons Dis* 2021; **11**(3): 937-47.
49. Donadio V, Wang Z, Incensi A, et al. In Vivo Diagnosis of Synucleinopathies: A Comparative Study of Skin Biopsy and RT-QuIC. *Neurology* 2021; **96**(20): e2513-e24.
50. Donadio V, Incensi A, Rizzo G, et al. Phosphorylated α -synuclein in skin Schwann cells: a new biomarker for multiple system atrophy. *Brain* 2022.
51. Alzghool OM, van Dongen G, van de Giessen E, Schoonmade L, Beaino W. α -Synuclein Radiotracer Development and In Vivo Imaging: Recent Advancements and New Perspectives. *Mov Disord* 2022; **37**(5): 936-48.
52. Xiang J, Tao Y, Xia Y, et al. Development of an α -synuclein positron emission tomography tracer for imaging synucleinopathies. *Cell* 2023.
53. Lees AJ, Tolosa E, Olanow CW. Four pioneers of L-dopa treatment: Arvid Carlsson, Oleh Hornykiewicz, George Cotzias, and Melvin Yahr. *Mov Disord* 2015; **30**(1): 19-36.
54. Walker Z, Jaros E, Walker RW, et al. Dementia with Lewy bodies: a comparison of clinical diagnosis, FP-CIT single photon emission computed tomography imaging and autopsy. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry* 2007; **78**(11): 1176-81.
55. McKeith I, O'Brien J, Walker Z, et al. Sensitivity and specificity of dopamine transporter imaging with ¹²³I-FP-CIT SPECT in dementia with Lewy bodies: a phase III, multicentre study. *Lancet Neurol* 2007; **6**(4): 305-13.
56. McCleery J, Morgan S, Bradley KM, Noel-Storr AH, Ansorge O, Hyde C. Dopamine transporter imaging for the diagnosis of dementia with Lewy bodies. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2015; **1**(1): Cd010633.
57. Thomas AJ, Attems J, Colloby SJ, et al. Autopsy validation of ¹²³I-FP-CIT dopaminergic neuroimaging for the diagnosis of DLB. *Neurology* 2017; **88**(3): 276-83.
58. Papathanasiou ND, Boutsiadis A, Dickson J, Bomanji JB. Diagnostic accuracy of ¹²³I-FP-CIT (DaTSCAN) in dementia with Lewy bodies: a meta-analysis of published studies. *Parkinsonism Relat Disord* 2012; **18**(3): 225-9.
59. Haber SN, Fudge JL, McFarland NR. Striatonigrostriatal Pathways in Primates Form an Ascending Spiral from the Shell to the Dorsolateral Striatum. *The Journal of Neuroscience* 2000; **20**(6): 2369-82.
60. Seibyl JP, Kuo P. What Is the Role of Dopamine Transporter Imaging in Parkinson Prevention Clinical Trials? *Neurology* 2022; **99**(7 Suppl 1): 61-7.
61. Colloby SJ, McParland S, O'Brien JT, Attems J. Neuropathological correlates of dopaminergic imaging in Alzheimer's disease and Lewy body dementias. *Brain : a journal of neurology* 2012; **135**(Pt 9): 2798-808.
62. Kraemmer J, Kovacs GG, Perju-Dumbrava L, Pirker S, Traub-Weidinger T, Pirker W. Correlation of striatal dopamine transporter imaging with post mortem substantia nigra cell counts. *Mov Disord* 2014; **29**(14): 1767-73.

63. Postuma RB, Iranzo A, Hu M, et al. Risk and predictors of dementia and parkinsonism in idiopathic REM sleep behaviour disorder: a multicentre study. *Brain : a journal of neurology* 2019; **142**(3): 744-59.
64. Wang C, Chen F, Li Y, Liu J. Possible predictors of phenoconversion in isolated REM sleep behaviour disorder: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry* 2022; **93**(4): 395-403.
65. Chahine LM, Brumm MC, Caspell-Garcia C, et al. Dopamine transporter imaging predicts clinically-defined α -synucleinopathy in REM sleep behavior disorder. *Annals of clinical and translational neurology* 2021; **8**(1): 201-12.
66. Siderowf A, Jennings D, Stern M, et al. Clinical and Imaging Progression in the PARS Cohort: Long-Term Follow-up. *Movement disorders : official journal of the Movement Disorder Society* 2020; **35**(9): 1550-7.
67. Jennings D, Siderowf A, Stern M, et al. Conversion to Parkinson Disease in the PARS Hypoemic and Dopamine Transporter-Deficit Prodromal Cohort. *JAMA neurology* 2017; **74**(8): 933-40.
68. Marek K, Seibyl J, Eberly S, et al. Longitudinal follow-up of SWEDD subjects in the PRECEPT Study. *Neurology* 2014; **82**(20): 1791-7.
69. Roberta B, Paolo B, Massimo F, Roberto E. Unexpected ((123)I)FP-CIT SPECT findings: SWIDD, SWEDD and all DAT. *J Neurol* 2022; **269**(2): 758-70.
70. Marek K, Chowdhury S, Siderowf A, et al. Establishing a Parkinson's Disease Biomarker Cohort. *Annals of Clinical and Translational Neurology* 2018; **5**(12): 1460-77.
71. Stephenson D, Akalu M, Alexander R, et al. Critical Path for Parkinson's: Catalyzing Innovation for Parkinson's Clinical Trials through Data Sharing and Regulatory Science (P2.8-010). *Neurology* 2019; **92**(15 Supplement): P2.8-010.
72. Seibyl JP. Imaging Biomarkers for Central Nervous System Drug Development and Future Clinical Utility: Lessons from Neurodegenerative Disorders. *Journal of Nuclear Medicine* 2023; **64**(1): 12-9.
73. Mitchell T, Lehericy S, Chiu SY, Strafella AP, Stoessl AJ, Vaillancourt DE. Emerging Neuroimaging Biomarkers Across Disease Stage in Parkinson Disease: A Review. *JAMA Neurol* 2021; **78**(10): 1262-72.
74. Tudorascu DL, Minhas DS, Lao PJ, et al. The use of Centiloids for applying [(11)C]PiB classification cutoffs across region-of-interest delineation methods. *Alzheimers Dement (Amst)* 2018; **10**: 332-9.
75. Concha-Marambio L, Weber S, Farris CM, et al. Accurate Detection of α -Synuclein Seeds in Cerebrospinal Fluid from Isolated Rapid Eye Movement Sleep Behavior Disorder and Patients with Parkinson's Disease in the DeNovo Parkinson (DeNoPa) Cohort. *Mov Disord* 2023; **38**(4): 567-78.
76. Bidesi NSR, Vang Andersen I, Windhorst AD, Shalgunov V, Herth MM. The role of neuroimaging in Parkinson's disease. *J Neurochem* 2021; **159**(4): 660-89.
77. Book A, Guella I, Candido T, et al. A Meta-Analysis of α -Synuclein Multiplication in Familial Parkinsonism. *Front Neurol* 2018; **9**: 1021.
78. Jia F, Fellner A, Kumar KR. Monogenic Parkinson's Disease: Genotype, Phenotype, Pathophysiology, and Genetic Testing. *Genes (Basel)* 2022; **13**(3).
79. Orme T, Guerreiro R, Bras J. The Genetics of Dementia with Lewy Bodies: Current Understanding and Future Directions. *Curr Neurol Neurosci Rep* 2018; **18**(10): 67.
80. Bandres-Ciga S, Diez-Fairen M, Kim JJ, Singleton AB. Genetics of Parkinson's disease: An introspection of its journey towards precision medicine. *Neurobiol Dis* 2020; **137**: 104782.
81. Skrahina V, Gaber H, Vollstedt EJ, et al. The Rostock International Parkinson's Disease (ROPAD) Study: Protocol and Initial Findings. *Mov Disord* 2021; **36**(4): 1005-10.
82. Lee AJ, Wang Y, Alcalay RN, et al. Penetrance estimate of LRRK2 p.G2019S mutation in individuals of non-Ashkenazi Jewish ancestry. *Mov Disord* 2017; **32**(10): 1432-8.
83. Koch S, Laabs B-H, Kasten M, et al. Validity and Prognostic Value of a Polygenic Risk Score for Parkinson's Disease. *Genes* 2021; **12**(12): 1859.

84. Schneider SA, Alcalay RN. Neuropathology of genetic synucleinopathies with parkinsonism: Review of the literature. *Mov Disord* 2017; **32**(11): 1504-23.
85. Doherty KM, Silveira-Moriyama L, Parkkinen L, et al. Parkin disease: a clinicopathologic entity? *JAMA Neurol* 2013; **70**(5): 571-9.
86. Pouloupoulos M, Levy OA, Alcalay RN. The neuropathology of genetic Parkinson's disease. *Mov Disord* 2012; **27**(7): 831-42.
87. Goetz CG, Tilley BC, Shaftman SR, et al. Movement Disorder Society-sponsored revision of the Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS): scale presentation and clinimetric testing results. *Movement disorders : official journal of the Movement Disorder Society* 2008; **23**(15): 2129-70.
88. Regnault A, Boroojerdi B, Meunier J, Bani M, Morel T, Cano S. Does the MDS-UPDRS provide the precision to assess progression in early Parkinson's disease? Learnings from the Parkinson's progression marker initiative cohort. *J Neurol* 2019; **266**(8): 1927-36.
89. Boeve BF, Silber MH, Ferman TJ, et al. Clinicopathologic correlations in 172 cases of rapid eye movement sleep behavior disorder with or without a coexisting neurologic disorder. *Sleep medicine* 2013; **14**((8)): 754-62.
90. Goldstein DS, Isonaka R, Lamotte G, Kaufmann H. Different phenoconversion pathways in pure autonomic failure with versus without Lewy bodies. *Clin Auton Res* 2021; **31**(6): 677-84.
91. Koga S, Sekiya H, Kondru N, Ross OA, Dickson DW. Neuropathology and molecular diagnosis of Synucleinopathies. *Mol Neurodegener* 2021; **16**(1): 83.
92. Ayers JI, Lee J, Monteiro O, et al. Different α -synuclein prion strains cause dementia with Lewy bodies and multiple system atrophy. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2022; **119**(6).
93. Dickson DW. Parkinson's disease and parkinsonism: neuropathology. *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Med* 2012; **2**(8).
94. Garrido A, Fairfoul G, Tolosa E, Marti MJ, Ezquerra M, Green AJE. Brain and Cerebrospinal Fluid alpha-Synuclein Real-Time Quaking-Induced Conversion Identifies Lewy Body Pathology in LRRK2-PD. *Mov Disord* 2023; **38**(2): 333-8.
95. Kalia LV, Lang AE, Hazrati LN, et al. Clinical correlations with Lewy body pathology in LRRK2-related Parkinson disease. *JAMA Neurol* 2015; **72**(1): 100-5.
96. Tolosa E, Vila M, Klein C, Rascol O. LRRK2 in Parkinson disease: challenges of clinical trials. *Nature Reviews Neurology* 2020; **16**(2): 97-107.
97. Dickson DW. Neuropathology of Parkinson disease. *Parkinsonism Relat Disord* 2018; **46 Suppl 1**(Suppl 1): S30-s3.
98. al. SDe. Transforming Drug Development for Neurological Disorders: Proceedings from a Multidisease Area Workshop. *Neurotherapeutics* 2023; **in press**.
99. Klos KJ, Ahlskog JE, Josephs KA, et al. Alpha-synuclein pathology in the spinal cords of neurologically asymptomatic aged individuals. *Neurology* 2006; **66**(7): 1100-2.
100. D'Antonio F, Kane JPM, Ibañez A, et al. Dementia with Lewy bodies research consortia: A global perspective from the ISTAART Lewy Body Dementias Professional Interest Area working group. *Alzheimers Dement (Amst)* 2021; **13**(1): e12235.